

**FIGHTING AGAINST THE CORRUPTION IN UZBEKISTAN.
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF NEW ZEALAND AND UZBEKISTAN.**

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Annotation: As we know corruption hinders in each countries political, economical development and pulls down the moral, ethical and social values and progress of the government's folk. This article talks over the reasons , and ways of fighting with this type of deceit, strategies that are utilized to combat with corruption in Uzbekistan, and the strategies of New Zealand, which is taking the first place in corruption free countries of the world.

Keywords: corruption, Uzbekistan, New Zealand, analysis, strategy, crime.

Аннотация: Как мы знаем, коррупция препятствует политическому, экономическому развитию каждой страны и подрывает моральные, этические и социальные ценности и прогресс людей правительства. В данной статье рассказывается о причинах и способах борьбы с таким видом обмана, стратегиях, которые используются для борьбы с коррупцией в Узбекистане, и стратегиях Новой Зеландии, занимающей первое место среди свободных от коррупции стран мира.

Ключевые слова: коррупция, Узбекистан, Новая Зеландия, анализ, стратегия, преступность.

Annotasiya: Biz bilamizki, korrupsiya har bir mamlakatda siyosiy, iqtisodiy taraqqiyotga to'sqinlik qiladi va hukumat xalqining ma'naviy, axloqiy va ijtimoiy qadriyatlarini va taraqqiyotiga putur etkazadi. Ushbu maqolada ushbu firibgarlikka qarshi kurashning sabablari va usullari, O'zbekistonda korrupsiyaga qarshi kurashda qo'llanilayotgan strategiyalar hamda dunyoda korrupsiyadan xoli mamlakatlarda birinchi o'rinni egallab turgan Yangi Zelandiyaning strategiyalari haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: korrupsiya, O'zbekiston, Yangi Zelandiya, tahlil, strategiya, jinoyat.

Introduction

Corruption is not a modern crime its root are in the long history in each country. All the governments in the world are combating against this criminal. There are special testing and indexing organisation such as CPI (Corruptions Perceptions Index), that evaluate and give the grade or percentage of committing corruption in all countries. However many organizations fight against the corruption, it is know as one of the widely spread type of fraud in the governmental agencies of each country. According to the information of CPI New Zealand is taking the leading places in corruption-free countries list (in 2006, 2007, 2008, 2009 and 2010, sitting alone atop the rankings in 2009 and 2011, and sharing the top position again (with Denmark and Finland) in 2012 until nowadays). And Uzbekistan is ranking in the 140 place among the 180 countries in the world according to 2021 score in CPI. Many effort is given to work and destroy the corruption reasons and types in Uzbekistan, however it is according to the CPI we are still being a country of ranking in the lower stages. What did New Zealand to erupt the currution from the governance or what strategies were used is very attractive and fascinating, if we also use that kind of strategic plans in our government will it work or what works are done to improve political, economical and social process to combat with the corruption? These questions are very essential to know and obey all rules do not commit such kids of crimes is must do actions.

This article tries to find out suitable responses to this questions. Furthermore, I give several different ways of tackling with it and the conditions of my faculty, is in the universities of Uzbekistan still corruption is processing or not?

What is the corruption?

By giving the relevant data about corruption, it is defined by many scholars differently. More precisely corruption is according to the World Bank, corruption is "the abuse of public office for private gain." In this instance it is challenging to give precise definitions of "public office" in the neopatrimonial political-economic system of Uzbekistan. The line separating the public and private sectors is not as

clear as it once was, and people with no established public position may be given the discretionary power to influence governmental decisions. Therefore, we adopt the definition of bribery established by various EU organizations, which refers to "the abuse of power for private gain, corruption in both the public and private sectors, as well as issues with cronyism, nepotistic hiring practices, and conflicts of interest. Corruption is the fraud of giving money or gift for the governmental agencies and people for their work as an additional profit, except from their salary that they take from the government.

New Zealand.

Why New Zealand is permanently staying in the top rank of CPI, what they are doing to maintain it? Understandably, much of the opinion on corruption in the country has been influenced by the truth that New Zealand has regularly maintained its top or almost top status on the CPI over the past 25 years. However, a more impartial, well-rounded analysis should better inform this commentary. A historical, less monocultural understanding of how the foundation of today's largely corrupt New Zealand was the betrayal of the Treaty of Waitangi, the taking of Maori land, and the suppression of Maori language and culture until the 1970s.[1] The causes and factors that influenced to New Zealand being a non- corruption country were free education in schools, generally clear and progressive taxation, and high level of gender equality [2, 26] however there were many problems in achieving today's status all over the world (for instance, the contemporary Zealand establishment circumstance 1852, the establishment circumstance 1986, the expenditure of Rights circumstance 1986, and the Electoral circumstance 1993, and also—perhaps bounteous importantly—on the phylogenesis of constitutive conventions. It would contemplate circumstances much as: the extinguishment of the territories in 1876; Massey's Cossacks of 1913; the passageway of the universal accommodation circumstance 1912; the governmental riotous behaviour during the considerable Depression;).

With reference to the latter, anti-money laundering legislation has been at the vanguard of cosmopolitan anti-corruption exertions on top of the yesteryear many decades, on the other hand contemporary Zealand's behindhand appropriation of this legislation compulsory exceptional experiencing of anesthetic firms,16 virtually of which chalk up been intermeshed in high-pitched levels of strange trade, manifestly without formal/legal examination of intercontinental permissible averages in combatting corruption.[3] Not only these reasons, but the people's worldview their opinions and effort in maintaining the status in CPI and so on.

Uzbekistan.

During the years of independence many effort was payed to combat against the corruption in our country. Our first president Islam Karimov and the current president Shavkat Mirziyoyev are trying to control the corruption and fight against it widely. A awe-inspiring exemplification of this, on February 7, 2017, the President's regulation "On the procedure of instrumentality in five-spot antecedence spaces of exploitation of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" was adopted, which is aimed at combating corruption, extremism and terrorism. content 2. 4 of this procedure cry out on officials to appropriate supplementary magnitudes to engagement churchgoing extremism, terrorism, and unionised crime, extremely as come around magnitudes to engagement putrefaction in the time to come years.[4] As education system is renewing and the government documents are digitised, the corruption opportunities are becoming less and less. In our university also as Hemis System internalized , the education system became corruption-free. Each branch of the government moving to the digitized report and working system. Most citizens of the Republic of the Uzbekistan is muslims, that religion strongly stands against the corruption and other types of crime, furthermore by internalizing the love and patriotic to the motherland efforts to flourish and develop the government by every sphere we may remove corruption from our country fully.

Conclusion.

To sum up our opinions, New Zealand being in the top of Corruption- free countries in the world, and there was much effort to maintain the status of the government. As New Zealand Uzbekistan is paying more attention to the strategies to combat with the corruption. Nowadays, the process of fighting with the corruption is working, one of the example can be this kind of competition to internalize the negative effect of corruption and fight for it. As a citizens of this country we must endeavour to prevent corruption from our country and increase the rank in Indexing organisations and believe to see the Uzbekistan in the first place as New Zealand.

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